

Fluorescent Schiff Base Chemosensors for Selective Ion Detection: A Brief Review

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Abstract

In the field of supramolecular chemistry, the detection of ions by using fluorescence and absorption techniques have gained significant importance due to their simplicity, high sensitivity and selectivity, low cost, detection limit, rapid response, and applicability to bioimaging. In recent years, Schiff-based receptors have been developed for the detection of various ions. This study mainly focuses on the fluorescent sensors which are based on Schiff base.

Keywords: Chemosensor, Schiff base, Fluorescence, Molecular recognition.

Introduction

In chemistry, environment, medicine and biology, cations play a vital role. In biological processes such as maintaining potentials across cell membranes, triggering muscle contraction, metal cations play an important role. On the other hand, some cations, such as lead and mercury, can cause harmful effects to the human body and the environment. In medical diagnostics, catalysis, environmental chemistry and physiology, several neutral and ionic species find extensive applications [1,2]. Excess accumulation of toxic ions may cause some severe neurodegenerative diseases, such as Parkinson's disease, Alzheimer's disease, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), and Wilson's disease in the human body.

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From above it is clear that detection of ions is necessary either they are useful or harmful. Fluorescent molecular sensors are used for detecting ions. Since fluorescent sensors are highly selective and easy to operate, they play an important role in many areas and disciplines. The molecular recognition of cations and anions by using absorption and fluorescence technique are receiving great interest in the field of supramolecular chemistry [3-6]. Cation complexation chemistry has played a significant role in the origin of the field of molecular recognition, since in many areas, cations play an important role. For the detection of cations, anions and biomolecules wide range of highly selective and sensitive chemosensors have been developed [7, 8].

The present review highlights recent progress in Schiff base fluorescent probes used for sensing biologically and environmentally significant ions.

Sensors for Nickel

Liu *et al.* reported a highly selective colorimetric chemosensor (**1**) for detection of Ni²⁺ ions in aqueous system DMSO-H₂O (v/v = 1:1, pH= 7.4). The addition of 10 equivalent of Ni²⁺ to the aqueous solution of probe (**1**) results into a dramatic colour change from yellow to red. Absorbance spectra of probe (**1**) showed a new peak at about 525 nm. Titration plots in UV-visible spectra revealed 1:1 stoichiometry between (**1**) and Ni²⁺. Interference study shows that no significant changes in the UV-visible spectra was found with and without the other competing metal ions. The detection limit was found to be 2.2×10^{-7} M. [9].

Fegadeet *al.* reported a fluorescent receptor (**2**) for the determination of Ni²⁺ in semi-aqueous media DMSO-H₂O (1:1, v/v) solvent system. Upon addition of Ni²⁺ ion solution

prepared in distilled water to the aqueous solution of receptor (2) gave remarkable fluorescent enhancement. Also, addition of 10 equivalent of Ni^{2+} to the aqueous solution of probe (2) causes color change from colorless to yellow. Interference study showed that interference of other tested metal ion in the detection of Ni^{2+} was insignificant. Job's plot experiment indicates the formation of 1:1 complex between probe (2) and Ni^{2+} [10].

(1)

(2)

Sensors for Zinc

Khairnar *et al.* reported a highly selective fluorescent 'turn on' chemosensor (3) for the detection of Zn^{2+} in DMSO- H_2O (90:10, *v/v*) solvent. The weak fluorescence of probe (3) was enhanced with red shift from 360 nm to 385nm ($\Delta\lambda=25$). The probe (3) was successfully applied for detection of Zn^{2+} in live HeLa cells. Interference study shows that probe (3) has high selectivity toward Zn^{2+} even in the presence of same concentration of other metal ions. Job's plot indicates 1:1 binding ratio between Zn^{2+} and probe (3). The detection limit was found to be 0.67 μM [11].

Tayade *et al.* reported a novel chemosensor (4) based on isonicotiamide for the detection of Zn^{2+} . The probe (4) also shows selectivity towards HSO_4^- . Weakly fluorescent probe (4) showed highly selective enhancement in the emission wavelength at 470 nm for

Zn^{2+} . Interference study showed that no significant variation was observed in the fluorescence of probe (4) with Zn^{2+} in the presence and absence of other cations. LOD of probe (4) as a fluorescent sensor for the analysis of Zn^{2+} was found to be 3.81 nM. The fluorescence properties of probe (4) were effectively clarified by two chemical input (Zn^{2+} and HSO_4^-) OR INHIBIT type logic gates at molecular level [12].

(3)

(4)

Sensors for Copper

Yeh *et al.* reported a coumarin-based sensitive and selective fluorescent sensor (5) for the detection of Cu^{2+} . In presence of Cu^{2+} probe (5) shows significant fluorescence quenching. Probe (5) upon addition of Cu^{2+} shows visible colour change from yellow to orange. Titration of Cu^{2+} with probe (5) shows that the absorbance at 487 nm decreased and new band at 440 nm was produced. Interference study shows that in presence of other competing metal ions no significant changes were observed in fluorescence spectra of probe (5) with Cu^{2+} . Job's plot revealed that 2:1 binding stoichiometry between Cu^{2+} and probe (5). The probe has limit of detection of $0.27\mu M$. Moreover, probe (5) could be successfully used as a fluorescent probe for detection of Cu^{2+} in living cells [13].

Yang *et al.* reported a colorimetric and fluorescent sensor (**6**) for Cu^{2+} detection in methanol-water (3/7, v/v) solvent system. Upon addition of Cu^{2+} to the probe (**6**) results into enhancement of the absorbance with formation of new peak at 552 nm and the color of the solution changes from colorless to pink. When more than 1.0 equivalent of Cu^{2+} was added the enhancement was saturated indicating that the binding mode was probably of 1:1 stoichiometry. Same conclusion about binding mode was obtained from Job's plot. The limit of detection for Cu^{2+} was found to be 0.096 μM . The competition experiments showed that no visible color change was observed and no change in the fluorescence spectra of probe (**6**) with Cu^{2+} were observed in the presence of other competing metal ions. The probe (**6**) was successfully applied for the fluorescence imaging in living cells [14].

(5)

(6)

Sanmartin-Metalobos *et al.* Synthesized a fluorescent probe (**7**) for detection of Cu^{2+} in aqueous samples. Spectroscopic studies show that probe (**7**) has higher affinity towards copper than other tested d-block metal ions. The detection limit of probe (**7**) for Cu^{2+} ion was found to be 8.7 nM [15].

Zhang *et al.* reported a novel chemosensor (**8**) for detection of Cu^{2+} ion in DMSO solution. Chemosensor (**8**) showed visible colour change from yellow to colorless on treatment with Cu^{2+} ion. The detection limit of chemosensor (**8**) for Cu^{2+} ion was found to be 4.87 nM. The binding constant for chemosensor (**8**) and Cu^{2+} ion was determined as $6.15 \times 10^{10} \text{ M}^{-1}$. Job's plot revealed that 1:2 binding stoichiometry of the complex between chemosensor (**8**) and Cu^{2+} ion [16].

Sensors for Magnesium

Kao *et al.* synthesized a turn on Schiff base fluorescent sensor (**9**) for the detection of Mg^{2+} . The probe (**9**) alone shows no significant emission after excitation at 353 nm but upon addition of Mg^{2+} , the fluorescence intensity of probe (**9**) increases significantly at the wavelength of 487 nm. Also, the probe (**9**) shows weak fluorescence enhancement upon addition of Ca^{2+} and Cd^{2+} . On the other hand, probe (**9**) shows very weak fluorescent band towards other metal ions. The probe (**9**) was successfully applied to detect Mg^{2+} in different sources of water such as lake, ground and tap water. Job's plot clearly shows 1:1 binding

stoichiometry between probe (9) and Mg^{2+} . The detection limit for probe (9) for the analysis of magnesium was found to be 19.1 ppb. The association constant for probe (9) and Mg^{2+} was determined as $1.91 \times 10^7 M^{-1}$ [17].

(9)

(10)

Wang *et al.* reported a turn on fluorescent sensor (10) based on Schiff base derivative for the detection of Mg^{2+} . Fluorescence spectra show that upon addition of Mg^{2+} ion to the probe (10) displayed significant fluorescence enhancement with emission maximum at 547 nm due to the Photo-Induced Electron Transfer (PET) effect. No other metal ion except Mg^{2+} shows change in the absorption and fluorescence spectra of probe (10). Interference study shows that even in presence of other competing metal ions probe (10) shows similar spectral changes that with Mg^{2+} ion. Based on Benesi-Hildebrand the association constant for complex (10)- Mg^{2+} were determine as $3.33 \times 10^4 M^{-1}$. The detection limit was found to be $5.16 \times 10^{-7} M$ [18].

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